

A Citation Analysis of Management and Senior Academic Administrators of Ahmadu Bello University Zaria from 2015 to 2020

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Abstract

The study was a citation analysis of the management staff of Ahmadu Bello University Zaria from 2015 to 2020. The survey research design was used in this study. The population for this study is 10. Comprising of the VC, DVC Admin, DVC Academic, UL, Dir. DAPM, Dean SPGS, Dean SAD, Dir. DUA, Dir. UHS and Dir. ICIC of Ahmadu Bello University Zaria-Nigeria. The entire population was used, therefore total enumeration or census method was adopted for this study because the population was not too large and the use of the total enumeration can eliminate any potential bias that may occur if a sample is selected and allowed for the generalization of the findings from the study. The researcher employed content analyses for collecting data in this study and used XML to search and collect data online. XML has been chosen for this case study for several reasons. The findings revealed that in March 2017, ResearchGate found fewer citations than Google Scholar but more than both Web of Science and Scopus. This held true for the dataset overall and for the six largest journals in it. ResearchGate correlated most strongly with Google Scholar citations, suggesting that ResearchGate is not predominantly tapping a fundamentally different source of data than Google Scholar. Nevertheless, preprint sharing in ResearchGate is substantial enough for authors to take seriously analysing more than one citation database will provide more effective results. The study concluded that google scholar is the highly cited index in the study. The results also show that google scholar has indexed impressively many citations and has become a major source of academic papers in the study area. However, the study recommended that the Management Staff of Ahmadu Bello University Zaria-Nigeria should improve citation quantity, and their intelligence work should be enhanced to provide a high level of literature utilization.

Keywords: Citation Analysis, Management Staff, University, Review of Literature

Introduction

Citation Analysis: The process whereby the impact or "quality" of an article is assessed by counting the number of times other authors mention it in their work. Citation analysis involves counting the number of times an article is cited by other works to measure the impact of a publication or author. citation is used synonymously with the term bibliographic reference. Citation analysis is consequently taken to represent the analysis of bibliographic references, which form part of the apparatus of scholarly communication. Knowledge about citing behaviour and the symbolic characteristics of citations is essential in order to determine whether it makes sense to use citation analysis in various areas of

application. Citation indicates the level of impact that a researcher is making in any field of endeavour. This impact is what gives visibility to the institution to which the researcher belongs. As the visibility of research has become more and more important to academics, higher institutions of learning, and the international community, the online audience has also become more significant for the researcher (Irenea, 2020). Research visibility is a function of the number of citations an article or publication accumulates over a period (Irenea, 2020). Citation is a measure that shows the number of times an article or publication has been used by other articles/publications (Ebrahim, Salehi, Embi, Tanha, and Gholizadeh, 2014).

Citation is the act of acknowledging or citing the work of an author. Citation is a text reference and acknowledgement of documented information. A scientifically written article comprises a reference section at the end where all references mentioned in the document are cited serially, and each reference is a citation (Nigam, A. & Nigam P.K., 2012). The process involving counting the number of times an article is cited by other works is known as Citation analysis. The citation index is a list of cited articles with citing articles in an orderly manner. When evaluating the relative contributions of several researchers or research groups, for example, citation counts are frequently used to back up research evaluations. However, citation analysis is a bibliographic database that provides citation links between documents (Hjørland, B. & Gnoli, C.). A citation index can come in two forms; paper-based database or electronic database. It is rarely known as a reference index.

Thelwall and Kousha (2017) cited in that in response, several alternatives have been proposed for early impact data. These include social web citations, Altmetrics (Priem, Taraborelli, Groth, & Neylon, 2010), and general web citations, webometrics (Vaughan & Shaw, 2003), as well as article download counts (Moed, 2005). Google Scholar is another logical alternative because its index can exploit public web documents, although its data can be time consuming to manually collect (Meho & Yang, 2007), when the Publish or Perish software (Harzing & Van Der Wal, 2009) is not suitable. Google Scholar seems to index more citations than Scopus (Moed, Bar-Ilan, & Halevi, 2016), which in turn has a bigger citation index than the Web of Science (WoS) (Mongeon & Paul-Hus, 2016). Another potential source is the citation data provided by ResearchGate since this is based upon an apparently large collection of publicly shared preprints, post prints and other documents.

ResearchGate is part of a general rise in the importance of professional social network sites (Brandão & Moro, 2017). It is the most regularly used professional website for scientists, and the third most popular in the social sciences, arts and humanities, but Google Scholar is more popular in all cases (Van Noorden, 2014) Academic social networks or search engines like Google Scholars, Academia.edu and ResearchGate appear to imitate established academic hierarchies the most. (Jordan, 2017), although they may give more space for younger researchers and women (Thelwall & Kousha, 2014). ResearchGate has allowed authors to upload their articles to the site since 2009 (ResearchGate, 2009). It added citation information to user profiles in 2013 (ResearchGate, 2013) and subsequently introduced the citation-related h-index (ResearchGate, 2016). As at April 2017, citation counts displayed for individual articles in

ResearchGate, along with the number of articles reads and comments by other researchers showed a marked increase. The wide use of the site and the extensive uploading to it has apparently made it a competitor for Google Scholar in terms of a citation index derived from publicly-shared research papers. Each academic member of ResearchGate receives an overall evaluation, known as the ResearchGate Score, which considers both their academic standing and their site activity.

Management/Senior Administrators of Ahmadu Bello University Zaria

The challenges of visibility for research and scholarship is real, and it is high time that universities, government agencies, and research policy makers need to do more for the future (Irenoa, 2020). And this is particularly so for academics who are engaged in administrative duties which takes a big part of the time needed for research activities. Ahmadu Bello University Zaria is a very large institution, that requires capacity for academics and administrators who run its affairs. Combining research and administration is a herculean task that would benefit more if there is a separation. Ahmadu Bello University Zaria has a structure and leadership whom will oversee the activities of that university “known as management”. In the University, the management is considered as policy and decision-making team who meet from time to time to take certain decisions on how best to run the university. Senior administrators in the university need a lot of information concerning the managing of university system (Usman, H. & Ukashatu, H. M 2019)

Figure 1 Management Hierarchy and Structure of Ahmadu Bello University Zaria.

The Vice Chancellor is the Chief Executive of the University he has two personnel assisting him namely: Deputy Vice Chancellor Administration and Deputy Vice Chancellor Academics. They assist the Vice Chancellor in terms of Administrative and academic activities and also assign one of them to act in his absence respectively. Registrar is the custodian of the University records and also secretary to the University council. Bursar is the account officer of the University who oversees all financial transaction of the University and also advice the Vice Chancellor on all financial regulations. University Librarian (UL) is in charge of the University Library. Director of Academic Planning (DAP) is in charge of coordinating and monitoring the academic activities of the University. Dean Student Affairs takes care of students' activities and welfare, Chief Internal Auditor monitors the financial transaction of the University,

Chief Security Officer monitors the security of lives and properties in the University community, Director of Estate monitors the University municipal services while Director of University Health Services (DUH) is in charge of health and environmental cleanliness in the University.

Problem statement

Citations are used as a measure of importance of an information source and enable users to gather information on the impact of journals as well as the scholar. The citation index is a bibliographic database that shows citation links between documents and the researcher. It helps the users to know which document is cited earlier than which. Also, they are made in such a way one can identify the cited document. Therefore, citation indexes are a tool for research evaluation. Management and academic administrators are categorized university Administrators such as Vice Chancellors, Deputy Vice Chancellors, University Librarian, Academic Directors, Deans and Heads of Departments they involve in teaching, learning, research, administration and community development. In order to be well equipped for their duties, they need to have vast knowledge through engaging in research for their own professional achievements (Ogunraku, 2010). Like every other academic staff of the university, some of the management and administrators' promotions require a peer review of published writings and presentations which may increase the university's visibility. Despite the paradigm shift in the research and publication process especially in the online environment, most of the research are not been cited in either Google Scholar, ResearchGate or Scopus citation index and no research was conducted to assess the most cited scholars in Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria. This is a great challenge, therefore, the need to carry out the research on the citation analysis

Research Objectives

1. To investigate the most citation index among the management and senior academic administrators of Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria
2. To outline the most visible scholars among the management and senior academic administrators of the Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria
3. To compare the level of research output among the management and senior academic administrators of Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria

Methodology

The survey research design was used in this study. The population for this study is 10. comprise all of the Management Staff of Ahmadu Bello University Zaria-Nigeria which Comprise of VC, DVC Admin, DVC Academic, UL, Dir. DAPM, Dean SPGS, Dean SAD, Dir. DUA, Dir. UHS and Dir. ICIC of Ahmadu Bello University Zaria-Nigeria. There was no sampling technique involved in this study because the researcher is interested in the total population, therefore total enumeration or census method

was adopted for this study. This is because the researcher considered the population as not too large to manage and that the use of the total enumeration can eliminate any potential bias that may occur if a sample is selected and allowed for the generalization of the findings from the study. The researcher employed the content analyses for collecting data in this study and used XML to search and collect data online. XML has been chosen for this case study for several reasons. 1. There's enough data available for conducting citation analysis studies. The core of the XML field of study belongs to computer science which can be applied in information science to collect data online. Frequency and simple percentage were the statics used in analyzing the data for the study.

Data presentation, Analysis and Discussion

The data shown in figure 1 to 3 were collated to enable the researcher provide answers to the research questions raised in the study.

Research Question One: Who is the most citation index by the management and academic administrators of Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria

figure 2: The citation index by the management and academic administrators of Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria.

Figure 2 Source: Google Scholar, ResearchGate and Scopus Citation (2020)

The result on Figure 2 showed that, the most citation index by the management and academic administrators of Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria is Google Scholar (3305), followed by ResearchGate (118) and Scopus citation (14). The implication of this analysis is that the management and academic administrators of Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria has very low citations between 2015 to 2020 in ResearchGate and Scopus citation index. according to Citation Reports Google Scholar is the most cited index. Results of this study also show that the use of ResearchGate has lowest report. This result indicates that the management and academic administrators of Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria have more citations in Google Scholar than in ResearchGate and Scopus citation index.

Research Question Two: Who is the most visible scholars within the management and academic administrators of the Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria?

Figure 3: below shows most visible scholars among the Management Staff

Figure 3 Source: Google Scholar, ResearchGate and Scopus Citation (2020)

The result on Figure 3 showed the most visible scholars within the management and academic administrators of the Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria is DVC academic, he has the highest number (2724) in term of research visibility, followed by Dir. ICIC with (906). Dir. DAPM HAS (803) and Dean SAD have (671). DVC academic recorded high scores. The management and academic administrators of Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria need to upload their researches online for global visibility, while other scholars are very low in term of visibility. This result shows that management and academic administrators of the Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria have not given serious attention to online publications or are not familiar with them.

Research Question Three: What is the level of research output by the management and academic administrators of Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria?

Figure 4 Source: Google Scholar, ResearchGate and Scopus Citation (2020)

This figure shows a citing author, his/her article, and its (modalized) references; other elements include authors of the cited documents, as well as an unidentified man and an “isolated reader.” It is unclear what, precisely, Latour means by “isolated reader.” However, for the sake of argument, let us suppose he means one who is unacquainted with the literature cited in the citing article. Now, if all readers were isolated readers like the one portrayed by Latour, it seems reasonable to assume that authors would be free to do whatever they needed to the earlier literature to align it as much as possible with their own arguments. However, as Nicolaisen (2004) has pointed out, this situation is highly unlikely and Latour’s assumption seems rather difficult to apply in this context. Most readers are not isolated in the sense given here. As Zunde (1971) noted, citation analysis has three main applications: Qualitative and quantitative evaluation of scientists, publications, and scientific institutions Modelling of the historical development of science and technology 1. 2. 3. Information search and retrieval Moreover, the introduction of two special citation-analytical techniques has paved the way for a fourth application: Knowledge organization based on bibliographic coupling (Kessler, 1963) and co-citation analysis (Marshakova, 1973; Small, 1973). Moed and Garfield (2003) added yet another dimension to the critique of the persuasion hypothesis in a study seeking to answer the question “how does the relative frequency at which authors in a research field cite ‘authoritative’ documents in the reference lists in their papers vary with the number of references such papers contain?”

Conclusion

The study has limited its lens to focus on 2015 to 2020 so as to empirically document the research productivities of the management staff coupled with their administrative duties. This report helps to give a bird’s eye view of the performance within this period. From what the research elicited from the various citation databases the administrators have shown varying levels of performance, although the study hasn’t documented the reasons for their differing performances in the analysis, it gives a picture of the challenges. High visibility and perceived impact of senior management sets the standard that subsequent leaders within the ivory towers will aspire to attain. The importance of this standard will generally spur younger leaders aspiring to high office, that work academic work does not stop upon attaining office.

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